

Discovery of two 19-Digit Palindromic Primes in the Decimal Expansion of π

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1 Introduction

On November 6, 2025, a computational search was conducted to identify palindromic prime numbers of length 19 within the first 10^{11} decimal digits of the mathematical constant π (approximately 3.141592653589793238462643383...). Using a modified C program with streaming capabilities to handle a 100 GB file containing the decimal expansion of π , two palindromic primes were discovered. A palindromic prime is a number that is both a palindrome (reads the same forwards and backwards) and a prime number. This document presents the positions of these palindromes in the decimal expansion of π . The detailed results, including certificates of primality, are available on ZENODO.

2 Results

The following list enumerates the two palindromic primes of length 19 found in the decimal expansion of π , along with their starting and ending positions (1-based indexing, relative to the first decimal digit after the decimal point in π):

1. **Palindrome:** **7240428184818240427**
Positions: 72075707767 – 72075707785
2. **Palindrome:** **9125010550550105219**
Positions: 78833628390 – 78833628408

3 Methodology

The search was performed using a custom C program employing the GMP library for arbitrary-precision arithmetic and multi-threading for efficiency. The program processed a 100 GB file containing 10^{11} decimal digits of π , using a streaming approach to minimize memory usage. The search targeted palindromes of length 19 within the interval $[1 - 10^{11}]$. Certificates of primality for each palindrome are archived on ZENODO for public access.